

**STUDY ON ROTATIONAL ENERGY SPECTRA OF NEUTRON-RICH ODD-ODD NUCLEI ^{102}Nb
AND ^{104}Nb USING THE PROJECTED SHELL MODEL**

Dong Yongsheng,

*JiNing Normal University, Science and Technology Department,
Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China*

Fund Project: Key Project of Natural Science Research of Jining Normal University (jsky202205)

Zhang Hongzhi

*JiNing Normal University, School of Mathematics and Statistic,
Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China*

Abstract

The projected shell model is employed to investigate the low-lying energy spectra of normally deformed neutron-rich niobium isotopes, ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb , with their quasiparticle configurations identified. The energy spectrum curves obtained from theoretical calculations show excellent agreement with those from experiments, demonstrating that the projected shell model is highly effective in studying the low-lying energy spectra of heavy nuclei.

Keywords: Projected Shell Model; Rotational Spectrum; Quasiparticle Configuration.

1 Introduction

Currently, neutron-rich nuclei in the $A=100$ mass region are a topic of interest both theoretically and experimentally. Phenomena such as their large quadrupole deformation [1,2], superdeformed ground states, identical bands [2,3], triaxial deformation [4,5], and shape changes [2,6] are particularly fascinating. To date, even-even nuclei and odd-A nuclei in this region have been studied in relative detail, while data on odd-odd nuclei remain scarce. Recently, a research group from Tsinghua University conducted experimental studies on the odd-odd nuclei ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb , and reported their energy spectra [7]. In the present work, we analyze these nuclei using the Projected Shell Model (PSM).

Proposed Wave Function:

$$\Psi_M^I = \sum_K f_K^I P_{MK}^I |\phi\rangle$$

Projection Operator:

$$\hat{P}_{MK}^I = \frac{2I+1}{8\pi^2} \int d\Omega D_{MK}^I(\Omega) \hat{R}(\Omega)$$

Hamiltonian:

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_0 - \sum_{\lambda} \frac{\chi_{\lambda}}{2} \sum_{\mu} \hat{Q}_{\lambda\mu}^+ \hat{Q}_{\lambda\mu} - G_M \hat{P}^+ \hat{P} - G_Q \sum_{\mu} \hat{P}_{\mu}^+ \hat{P}_{\mu}$$

Interaction Force χ is related to Deformation δ :

$$\chi_{\tau\tau'} = \frac{\delta \hbar \omega_{\tau} \hbar \omega_{\tau'}}{\hbar \omega_n \langle \hat{Q} \rangle_n + \hbar \omega_p \langle \hat{Q} \rangle_p}$$

G_M is determined by the odd-even mass difference:

$$G_M = [G_1 \mp G_2 \frac{N-Z}{A}] A^{-1}$$

"-" denotes a neutron, and "+" denotes a proton. G_Q is proportional to G_M , $G_Q \approx 0.2G_M$.

2.2 Multi-Particle State Angular Momentum Projection

Even-Even Nucleus:

$$\{\hat{P}_{MK}^I |0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ |0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_{\pi}^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ |0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ |0\rangle, \dots\}$$

Odd-Odd Nucleus:

$$\{\hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ |0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ |0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ |0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ \alpha_{\pi}^+ |0\rangle, \dots\}$$

Odd-Neutron Nucleus:

$$\{\hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ | 0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_\pi^+ \alpha_\pi^+ | 0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_\pi^+ \alpha_\pi^+ | 0\rangle, \dots\}$$

Odd-Proton Nucleus:

$$\{\hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_\pi^+ | 0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_\pi^+ | 0\rangle, \hat{P}_{MK}^I \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_v^+ \alpha_\pi^+ \alpha_\pi^+ | 0\rangle, \dots\}$$

Solving the Generalized Eigenvalue Equation:

$$\sum_{K'} (H_{KK'}^I - EN_{KK'}^I) f_{K'} = 0$$

Matrix Element:

$$H_{KK'}^I = \langle \phi | HP_{KK'}^I | \phi_{K'} \rangle$$

$$N_{KK'}^I = \langle \phi | P_{KK'}^I | \phi_{K'} \rangle$$

The Hamiltonian is diagonalized in the projected basis $\{P_{MK}^I | \phi_K \rangle\}$.

Energy:

$$E_K(I) = \frac{H_{KK}^I}{N_{KK}^I} = \frac{\langle \phi | HP_{KK}^I | \phi_{K'} \rangle}{\langle \phi | P_{KK}^I | \phi_{K'} \rangle}$$

3 Calculation of Rotational Energy Spectra of Odd-Odd Nuclei ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb Using PSM

Partial energy spectra of the ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb nuclei are taken from Reference [7]. In the PSM calculations, the parameters are set as follows: $G_1 = 20.25$, $G_2 = 16.20$, and $\gamma = 0.18$. According to Reference [11], for the ^{102}Nb nucleus, the deformation parameters are $\varepsilon_2 = 0.342$ and $\varepsilon_4 = 0.013$; for the ^{104}Nb nucleus, the deformation parameters are $\varepsilon_2 = 0.350$ and $\varepsilon_4 = 0.033$. The calculation results are shown in Figure 1. Through analysis, it can be concluded that for both the ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb nuclei, the low-energy bands with $k = 3$ are mainly dominated by the $1h_{11/2}$ quasi-neutron $5/2[532]$ and $1g_{7/2}$ quasi-proton $1/2[431]$ near the Fermi surface, i.e., dominated by the configuration $v5/2[532] \otimes \pi 1/2[431]$.

Figure 1(a): Partial Energy Spectra of the ^{102}Nb Nucleus Calculated Using PSM

Figure 1(b): Partial Energy Spectra of the ^{104}Nb Nucleus Calculated Using PSM

Figure 2(a): Band Crossing of the Ground Band and Quasiparticle Rotational Bands of the ^{102}Nb Nucleus Calculated Using PSM

Figure 2(b): Band Crossing of the Ground Band and Quasiparticle Rotational Bands of the ^{104}Nb Nucleus Calculated Using PSM

Figure 2 shows that the g-band represents the ground-state rotational bands of the ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb nuclei, the yrast band represents the yrast band, and the $\nu 5/2[532] \otimes \pi 1/2[431]$ band represents the two-quasiparticle rotational band.

4 Analysis and Summary

Through the calculation and analysis of the energy spectra of the neutron-rich odd-odd nuclei ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb , it is found that the theory well reproduces the experimental results. Furthermore, by analyzing the band crossing phenomenon between the ground band and the quasiparticle rotational bands (as shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b)), and comparing the contributions of each quasiparticle band to the formation of the yrast band, some very meaningful results are obtained. First, for the low-lying excitation spectra of ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb , in the low-spin region, the nuclear deformation mainly depends on the properties of the ground band, i.e., on the $\nu 1g_{7/2} \otimes \pi 1g_{9/2}$ intrinsic states of quasiparticles; in other words, the $\nu 1g_{7/2} \otimes \pi 1g_{9/2}$ intrinsic states of quasiparticles contain abundant information that affects nuclear deformation. Second, with the increase in spin, when the spin reaches $I > 5\hbar$, the odd neutron and odd proton in the high- j intruder orbitals near the Fermi surface form quasiparticles. As a result, a band crossing phenomenon occurs between the ground band and the quasiparticle rotational bands, and the corresponding kinematic moment of inertia changes to a certain extent with spin. Meanwhile, we find that these low-lying deformed bands are mainly caused by the

high- j intruder states $1h_{11/2}$ and $1g_{7/2}$ located in the $N=5$ and $N=4$ harmonic oscillator shells; in particular, the discussion on the configuration of the quasiparticle excitation bands shows that the quasiparticles in the $\nu 5/2[532] \otimes \pi 1/2[431]$ orbitals are the main reason for the deformation of ^{102}Nb and ^{104}Nb .

References

1. E. Cheifetz, R.C. Thompson, J.B. Wilhelmy. Phys. Rev. Lett, 1970, 25:38.
2. J.H. Hamilton, Prog. part. Nucl. Phys, 1985, 15:107.
3. J.H. Hamilton. Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys, 1995, 35:635.
4. K. Shizuma, H. Lawin, K. Sistemich *et al.* Z, Phys, 1983, A311:71.
5. Luo Y.X, J O Rasmussen, I Stefanescu, A Gelberg *et al.* J.Phys.G: Nucl. Part. Phys, 2005, 31:1303.
6. N. Fotiades, J.A. Cizewski, D.P. McNabb *et al.* Phys. Rev, 1998, C 58:1997 - 2001.
7. Wang J.G, Zhu S.J, J.H. Hamilton. *et al.* Phys.Rev, 2008, C78:014313.
8. K.Hara, Sun Yang, Int. J. Mod.Phys, 1995, E4, 637.
9. S.G. Nilsson, Dan. Mat. Fys. Medd. 29,1955,nr. 16.
10. Sun Yang, Kenji Hara. Computer Physics Communications, 1997,104: 245-258.
11. P. Möller, J.R. Nix, W.D. Myers, *et al.* Suiatecki/Nuclear Masses 93-96.